

Supporting Information

A geometrically well-defined and systematically tunable experimental model to transition from planar to mesoporous perovskite solar cells

Dirk Döhler,[†] Pascal Büttner,[†] Florian Scheler,^{†,‡} Dominik Thiel,[¶] Bianka Puscher,[¶] Sebastian Bochmann,[†] Julian Mitrovic,[†] Pablo P. Boix,[§] Dirk M. Guldi,[¶] Ignacio Mínguez-Bacho,[†] and Julien Bachmann^{*,†}

[†]*Chemistry of Thin Film Materials, Department of Chemistry and Pharmacy, Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, Cauerstr. 3, Erlangen, 91058 Germany*

[‡]*New address: Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin, Young Investigator Group Perovskite Tandem Solar Cells, 12489 Berlin, Germany*

[¶]*Interdisciplinary Center for Molecular Materials (ICMM), Department of Chemistry and Pharmacy, Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, Egerlandstr. 3, 91058 Erlangen, Germany.*

[§]*Instituto de Ciencia de Materiales, Universidad de Valencia, 46980 Paterna, Spain*

E-mail: julien.bachmann@fau.de

Figure S1: Scanning electron micrograph (top view) of (a) an aluminium layer with insufficient thermal control during deposition, showing a rough surface with big grains; (b) anodized and widened pores of such aluminum films.

Figure S2: Scanning electron micrograph (top view) of an AAO template directly after anodization at 60 V without pore widening done.

Figure S3: Tauc Plots of (a) the TiO_2 or (b) the perovskite absorption edge for all different substrates. The inserts show close ups of the intercepts with the x-axis.

Figure S4: Steady-state fluorescence measurements; (a) Emission spectra of perovskite deposited on the different electrodes and on glass; (b) Photoluminescence plotted against pore length (p corresponds to a planar sample, mp corresponds to a sample with mp- TiO_2); (c) Excitation spectra of perovskite deposited on the different electrodes.

Figure S5: Thickness of the compact perovskite layer on top of the AAO structure plotted against the pore length.

Figure S6: Backscattered electron SEM cross section micrograph showing the perfect filling of a sample with 390 nm pore length.

Figure S7: Performance parameters for the J - V forward curves measured from -0.2 V to 1.2 V; (a) Efficiency, (b) fill factor, (c) J_{sc} , and (d) V_{oc} .

Figure S8: (a) V_{oc} (obtained from a 3 min OCP measurement) plotted against light intensity; (b) Ideality factors extracted from the linear fit shown in (a) for all measured geometries and pore lengths.

Figure S9: Performance parameters of the J - V curves of AAO PSCs without TiO_2 ALD for the forward (a, c, e, g) and the reverse cycle (b, d, f, h); (a,b) Efficiency, (c,d) fill factor, (e,f) J_{sc} , and (g,h) V_{oc} .

Figure S10: J - V curves recorded at various scan rates for various samples, with hysteresis index values extract from them.

Figure S11: Equivalent circuit model used to fit the impedance data from Fig. 6.